

Germination and vigor of hydrated rice seeds after 3 periods of storage. Tamil Nadu, India.

Cultivar duration	Parameter	Initial	After storage						Biological loss (%)		
			8 mo		12 mo		32 mo		Control	Hydrated	
			Control	Hydrated	Control	Hydrated	Control	Hydrated			
Short	Germination (%)	86	82	90	<i>ADT31</i> 73		89	45	85	47.7	1.2
	Root length (cm)	19.5	17.6	22.1	15.0	20.0	9.2	17.8	52.8	8.7	
Medium	Germination (%)	90	84	95	<i>Bhavani</i> 75		86	16	85	82.2	5.6
	Root length (cm)	18.2	16.0	17.6	15.0	19.5	10.4	18.2	42.8	–	
Long	Germination (%)	89	86	94	<i>CO40</i> 78		88	27	87	69.7	2.2
	Root length (cm)	20.7	18.9	21.1	17.7	20.2	11.5	19.0	44.4	8.2	

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology

Influence of wild plant and crop residues on rice yield

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Plant residues and farmyard manure are added to soils to improve their organic matter content and productivity. This traditional agricultural practice has primarily been used to increase soil humus content, water-holding capacity, water infiltration rate, aeration, and porosity; to ameliorate soil temperature; and to supply some essential plant nutrients.

In a pot study, we evaluated the effect of incorporating residues of mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*), withania (*Withania somnifera*), and country mallow (*Abutilon indicum*) with rice (*Oryza sativa*) husks and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and rice straw, neem (*Azadirachta indicum*) leaves, and farmyard manure on straw and grain yields of rice. Soil had pH 7.6, 0.95%

organic C, 0.073% N, 9.7% CaCO₃, 0.15% TSS. Each pot held 8 kg soil.

For the wild plants, treatments were 3 g residue/kg soil (about 6 t/ha) plus 25 mg N/kg (about 50 kg N/ha). For the crop residues, treatments were 3 g residue/kg soil plus 50 mg N/kg soil. Each pot also received 25 mg P/kg soil. Rice cultivar Shadab was transplanted at 4 seedlings/pot. Pots were arranged in a randomized block design with four replications. N application was lower for the wild plants because their very high antibiotic activities tended to inhibit nitrification.

Effect of incorporating plant residues on rice straw and grain yields.^a

Treatment ^b (g/pot)	Straw yield	Grain yield (g/pot)
Control (no residue)	17.45 c	11.70 b
Mesquite	28.80 a	24.97 a
Withania	23.92 b	19.62 a
Country mallow	24.62 b	22.00 a
Rice husk	16.05 c	11.62 b
Wheat straw	16.92 c	10.75 b
Rice straw	18.05 c	12.10 b
Neem leaf	25.22 b	20.67 a
Farmyard manure	17.92 c	10.22 b

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (DMRT p<0.5). ^b Plant residue and farmyard manure were applied at 3 g/kg soil.

Straw and grain yield increased significantly with incorporation of mesquite, withania, and country mallow residues, and of neem leaf (see table). ■

Effect of seeding rate on dry matter production and nitrogen accumulation of *Sesbania rostrata*

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Increased crop seeding rates result in increased plant competition for nutrients and light. We evaluated the effect of different seeding rates on dry matter production and N accumulation in *Sesbania rostrata*, a stem-nodulating legume and potential green manure crop for lowland rice.

The field experiment was conducted in 1987 wet season. Soil was a Maahas clay (Tropaquept) with pH 6.3; 11 g organic C/kg; 1.2 g total N/kg; and cation exchange capacity, 34 cmol/kg. P (20 kg/ha) as single superphosphate was broadcast and incorporated before seeding. Seeding rates were 20, 30, 40, and 50 kg sesbania seeds/ha, laid out in a factorial randomized complete block design with four replications. Plot size was 20 m².

Sesbania seeds pretreated for 30 min with concentrated sulfuric acid were broadcast into well-leveled, water-saturated soil. The field was kept saturated to 7 d after seeding, then flooded to 0.05 m.

Sesbania was harvested 45 d after seeding. Plant fresh and dry weights were measured and plant density determined from a 7-m² area. A subsample (4 × 1 m per plot) was taken to determine leaf and stem dry matter separately and to analyze N concentrations in leaf and stem. Total N accumulation was calculated.

N concentrations in leaf and stem did not differ significantly with seeding rate (see table). Seeding at 40 kg/ha gave the highest total N accumulation per plant (114 kg N/ha), and highest fresh and dry matter production. Seeding at 50 kg/ha gave lower fresh and dry matter production and N accumulation than seeding at 40 kg/ha.

Plant density, dry matter production, N concentration, and N accumulation of *Sesbania rostrata* at different seeding rate IRRI farm, Philippines, 1987 wet season.

Seeding rate (kg/ha)	Dry matter (mg/ha)		Plant density (plants/m ²)	Leaf N (g/kg)	Stem N (g/kg)	Total plant N (kg/ha)
	Leaf	Stem				
20	1.2	2.7	55	46	9	81
30	1.3	3.0	70	46	8	85
40	1.6	4.1	107	47	9	114
50	1.5	3.9	119	46	8	100
LSD (0.05)	0.1	0.3	10	2	1	8

These results suggest that the higher plant densities resulting from seeding rates above 40 kg/ha decrease organic matter production and N accumulation of sesbania plants. A plant density of 100 plants/m² seems to be optimum for maximum N accumulation.

To achieve a plant density of about 100 plants/m², seeding rates may have to be adjusted for soil textures, climates, and field conditions. ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effects of a growth regulator on rice seedling growth

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Growth regulator Triacantanol has been found effective in increasing biomass production in cereals and vegetable crops.

Triacantanol increases plant height and weight within a few days of application and stimulates nutrient assimilation.

Seeds of semidwarf IET4094 and IR42 and tall indica NC492 rice varieties were soaked 1 h before sowing in 3 concentrations of TRIA (n-Triacantanol): 0.01, 0.10, and 1.00 ppm, with three replications. Root length, root volume,

seedling height, seedling dry weight, and leaf number were recorded 25 d after seeding.

In general, seedlings treated with TRIA were superior to those with no treatment (see table). Late-maturing NC492 and IR42 showed better results than medium-maturing IET4094 in all treatments, for all characters. No toxic, abnormal, or atypical morphological changes were observed at the concentrations used. ■

Effect of n-Triacantanol on rice seedling characters.

n-Triacantanol (mg/liter)	Root length (cm/plant)			Root volume (ml/plant)			Seedling height (cm/plant)			Leaf no. per seedling			Seedling dry wt (mg/plant)		
	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492
0.00	21.2	15.3	17.6	0.2	0.1	0.2	27.4	20.2	37.4	4.9	4.1	4.2	114	137	211
0.01	21.8	21.5	19.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	27.7	25.2	38.6	4.9	4.9	4.7	171	219	237
0.10	21.8	18.6	20.4	0.3	0.2	0.5	27.6	24.1	39.5	5.0	4.9	4.4	181	207	253
1.00	21.8	18.6	18.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	27.6	23.9	37.8	5.0	4.9	4.5	186	202	217
CV (%)	7.8			10.1			4.2			2.9			5.8		
LSD (0.05)	2.6			0.1			2.1			0.2			18		

Fertilizer management

Greenhouse evaluation of urea supergranules (USG) containing diammonium phosphate (DAP) for transplanted rice

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Serious losses of fertilizer N and P to runoff are common in transplanted rainfed ricefields of small farmers in South and Southeast Asia. Losses occur primarily because farmers are unable to properly incorporate fertilizers into soils with varying depths of nonflowing or

flowing floodwaters. A ready-made, balanced NP fertilizer and an alternative application method are needed.

Phosphatic fertilizers containing Ca(H₂PO₄)₂·H₂O (such as single or triple superphosphate [TSP]) are not compatible with urea because of an adduct formation that leads to poor physical quality and caking of USG briquettes. DAP, a common fertilizer for transplanted rice in tropical rice-growing countries, is compatible for preparation of USG. Agronomically, deep placement of USG is efficient in transplanted rice.

We conducted a greenhouse experiment to evaluate basal deep-placed USG containing DAP as NP fertilizer in transplanted rice. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Soil was Vernon clay (Typic

Ustochrept, pH 8.0, CEC 33.0 cmol_c/kg), which in earlier experiments had responded to applied N and P. For a blanket basal application, 100 mg K/kg (as KC1) and 25 mg Zn/kg (as ZnSO₄) were incorporated into the soil before transplanting.

Four hills (three 3-wk-old seedlings/hill) of IR36 were transplanted (20- × 20-cm spacing) in 2-wk presubmerged and puddled soil (32 kg air-dried basis) in a wooden box (40- × 40- × 30-cm inside dimensions) with plastic lining. USG containing DAP (as tablets) was prepared by compacting a mixture of prilled urea (PU) and DAP in a 1:2 proportion. The amounts of N and P used (19.3 mg N/kg and 10.3 mg P/kg, equivalent to 40 kg N and 21 kg P/ha on area basis) were on the steep portion of their response curves for the soil used.